

MONITORING SADRŽAJA I BIODOSTUPNOSTI TEŠKIH METALA U SEDIMENTIMA U CILJU PROCJENE RIZIKA OD ZAGAĐIVANJA PODZEMNIH VODA

MONITORING OF HEAVY METAL CONTENT AND BIOAVAILABILITY IN SEDIMENTS FOR GROUNDWATER POLLUTION RISK ASSESSMENT

IZVOD

U ovom radu ispitan je sadržaj i biodostupnost teških metala u sedimentima s ciljem procjene rizika od njihovog potencijalnog uticaja na podzemne vode. Istraživanje je sprovedeno na pilot lokaciji duž kanala Begej, gdje su formirane dvije eksperimentalne deponije sa izmuljenim sedimentom, koje predstavljaju različite tipove zagađenja: starije, stabilizovano (Deponija 1) i svježije deponovano (Deponija 2). Tokom višegodišnjeg monitoringa (2021–2024) praćene su promjene u ukupnom sadržaju i biodostupnosti hroma i kadmijuma u sedimentu. Rezultati su pokazali da su koncentracije metala bile značajno više na eksperimentalnim deponijama u poređenju s kontrolom, pri čemu su najviše vrijednosti zabilježene na svježem sedimentu. Analiza BCR sekvencijalne ekstrakcije potvrdila je da se biodostupnost metala smanjuje s vremenom – u starijem sedimentu dominiraju stabilne frakcije, dok su u svježem prisutniji mobilni oblici, naročito kadmijuma, koji nose najveći rizik od migracije u podzemne vode. Višegodišnja fitoremedijacija doprinijela je dodatnoj stabilizaciji metala u površinskom sloju. Dobijeni rezultati potvrđuju da procjena rizika mora uključiti analizu biodostupnih oblika metala, a ne samo njihov ukupni sadržaj.

Ključne reči: sediment, podzemna voda, teški metali, biodostupnost, procjena rizika

ABSTRACT

This study examined the content and bioavailability of heavy metals in sediments to assess the risk of their potential impact on groundwater. The research was conducted at a pilot site along the Begej Canal, where two experimental landfills with dredged sediment were established, representing different contamination types: older, stabilized (Landfill 1) and freshly deposited (Landfill 2). During multi-year monitoring (2021–2024), changes in the total content and bioavailability of chromium and cadmium in the sediment were evaluated. The results showed that metal concentrations were significantly higher at the experimental landfills compared to the control site, with the highest values recorded in the freshly deposited sediment. The BCR sequential extraction analysis confirmed that metal bioavailability decreases over time - stable fractions dominate in the older sediment, while more mobile forms, particularly cadmium, prevail in the fresh one, posing the greatest risk of migration into groundwater. Multi-year phytoremediation contributed to additional stabilization of metals in the surface sediment layer. The findings confirm that risk assessment must include the analysis of bioavailable metal forms, not only their total concentrations.

Keywords: sediment, groundwater, heavy metals, bioavailability, risk assessment

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1. UVOD

Ubrzan industrijski i poljoprivredni razvoj, započeo u XX vijeku, donio je brojne koristi društvu, ali je istovremeno prouzrokovao značajne negativne efekte po životnu sredinu. Intenzivna eksploatacija prirodnih resursa, nepravilno odlaganje otpada i ispuštanje neprečišćenih otpadnih voda doveli su do zagađenja vazduha, vode i zemljišta, što direktno utiče na kvalitet života, zdravlje ljudi, kao i na biljni i životinjski svijet (Yuan i sar., 2021). U tom kontekstu, kontrola prisustva i ponašanja zagađujućih supstanci postala je ključna za očuvanje ekosistema, a naročito vodnih resursa. Teški metali spadaju među najopasnije zagađujuće supstance zbog svoje toksičnosti, nemogućnosti degradacije i sposobnosti bioakumulacije u živim organizmima (Briffa i sar., 2020; Dash i sar., 2021). Njihova rastvorljivost i mobilnost omogućavaju kretanje kroz zemljište i vodene ekosisteme, čime se povećava rizik od kontaminacije površinskih i podzemnih voda (Donázar-Aramendía i sar., 2020). Poseban problem predstavlja dugotrajno prisustvo teških metala u sedimentima, gdje se akumuliraju tokom vremena i mogu postati sekundarni izvor zagađenja kada dođe do promjene hemijskih ili fizičkih uslova sredine (Jahanirad i sar., 2023).

Sediment ima ključnu ulogu u zaštiti životne sredine jer djeluje kao rezervoar za akumulaciju različitih zagađujućih supstanci, ali i kao posrednik u njihovoj razmjeni između vodenog i kopnenog ekosistema (Zhang i sar., 2021). Zbog potrebe za održavanjem plovnosti vodnih puteva, prevencijom poplava i unapređenjem vodnog režima, sediment se često uklanja procesom izmuljivanja. Ovaj proces, iako neophodan, stvara značajne količine materijala koje je potrebno pravilno tretirati ili odložiti. Ako je sediment zagađen, njegovo odlaganje na obalu rijeka ili okolno zemljište može dovesti do sekundarnog zagađenja, uključujući i rizik od migracije metala u podzemne vode (Maletić i sar., 2022; Svensson i sar., 2022).

S obzirom na to da se sastav i ponašanje teških metala u sedimentu mogu značajno mijenjati tokom vremena pod uticajem različitih fizičko-hemijskih i bioloških faktora, kao što su pH vrijednost, redoks potencijal, sadržaj organske materije i aktivnost mikroorganizama, neophodno je dugoročno praćenje njihovog sadržaja i biodostupnosti. Monitoring ovih parametara omogućava bolje razumijevanje dinamike metala u sedimentu, procjenu njihovog potencijala mobilizacije i identifikaciju faktora koji utiču na njihovu raspoloživost za transport u dublje slojeve zemljišta (Chen i sar., 2025; Kuang i sar., 2024). Posebno je važna procjena biodostupne frakcije

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid industrial and agricultural development that began in the 20th century has brought numerous benefits to society but has also caused significant negative effects on the environment. Intensive exploitation of natural resources, improper waste disposal, and the discharge of untreated wastewater have led to the pollution of air, water, and soil, directly affecting quality of life, human health, as well as plant and animal species (Yuan et al., 2021). In this context, monitoring the presence and behavior of pollutants has become crucial for ecosystem preservation, particularly regarding water resources. Heavy metals are among the most hazardous pollutants due to their toxicity, persistence, and ability to bioaccumulate in living organisms (Briffa et al., 2020; Dash et al., 2021). Their solubility and mobility enable movement through soil and aquatic systems, thereby increasing the risk of surface and groundwater contamination (Donázar-Aramendía et al., 2020). A particular concern is the long-term presence of heavy metals in sediments, where they accumulate over time and may become a secondary source of pollution when chemical or physical conditions change (Jahanirad et al., 2023).

Sediment plays a key role in environmental protection, acting both as a reservoir for the accumulation of various pollutants and as a mediator in their exchange between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems (Zhang et al., 2021). Due to the need to maintain waterway navigability, prevent flooding, and improve water management, sediment is often removed through the dredging process. Although necessary, this process generates large quantities of material that must be properly treated or disposed of. If the sediment is contaminated, its disposal along riverbanks or on nearby land can lead to secondary pollution, including the risk of metal migration into groundwater (Maletić et al., 2022; Svensson et al., 2022).

Given that the composition and behavior of heavy metals in sediment can change significantly over time under the influence of various physicochemical and biological factors, such as pH, redox potential, organic matter content, and microbial activity, long-term monitoring of their concentrations and bioavailability is essential. Monitoring these parameters enables a better understanding of metal dynamics in sediments, the assessment of their mobilization potential, and the identification of factors influencing their availability for transport into deeper soil layers (Chen et al., 2025; Kuang et al., 2024). Particularly important is the evaluation of the bioavailable

metala, budući da upravo ovaj dio predstavlja najveću prijetnju za migraciju u podzemne vode i ulazak u vodene tokove (Choudhary i sar., 2024).

Fitoremedijacija, kao ekološki prihvatljiv, efikasan i ekonomski isplativ pristup, sve više se koristi za sanaciju zemljišta i sedimenata zagađenih teškim metalima (Akpor i sar., 2014; Babu i sar., 2021). Ova metoda koristi sposobnost određenih biljnih vrsta da usvajaju, translociraju i transformišu zagađujuće supstance iz okoline. Posebno značajna je fitoekstrakcija, koja omogućava selektivno usvajanje metala putem korijena biljke i njihovu translokaciju u nadzemne dijelove biljke (Zeremski i sar., 2021; Yan i sar., 2020).

U ovom istraživanju analizirana su dva lokaliteta na koje je odložen izmuljeni sediment, gdje je tokom više uzastopnih godina praćen ukupni sadržaj i biodostupnost teških metala. Istovremeno je sproveden proces fitoremedijacije s ciljem smanjenja njihove koncentracije i ograničavanja mobilnosti. Višegodišnji monitoring omogućio je procjenu promjena u koncentracijama i frakcijskoj raspodjeli metala, što je ključno za razumijevanje njihovog ponašanja u sedimentu i procjenu rizika od migracije prema podzemnim vodama. Poseban značaj ovakvog pristupa ogleda se u činjenici da upravo biodostupna frakcija metala predstavlja najveću prijetnju za njihovo ispiranje i transport kroz zemljišni profil. Dobijeni rezultati omogućavaju sveobuhvatnu procjenu potencijalnog rizika po podzemne vode i predstavljaju osnovu za donošenje odluka u vezi sa daljim upravljanjem kontaminiranim lokalitetima.

2. EKSPERIMENTALNI DIO

Istraživanje je sprovedeno na pilot lokaciji u Srbiji, smještenoj duž kanala Begej u blizini srpsko–rumunske granice. Lokacija je podijeljena na dvije ograđene sekcije, nazvane Deponija 1 i Deponija 2 – površine oko 1200 m² svaka. Ove sekcije su formirane za odlaganje izmuljenog sedimenta iz kanala Begej, za koji su podaci o kvalitetu sedimenta prikupljeni u periodu 2003–2015 (Dalmacija i sar., 2006; Dubovina i sar., 2018) konstantno pokazivali da je sediment zagađen teškim metalima i specifičnim organskim polutantima. Deponija 1 sadrži sediment izmuljen 2017. godine, dok je Deponija 2 prekrivena svježim sedimentom deponovanim krajem 2021. godine. Na taj način obezbijeđeni su uslovi za sprovođenje višegodišnjeg eksperimenta praćenja ponašanja teških metala u sedimentu i njihove mobilnosti tokom procesa fitoremedijacije.

fraction of metals, as this portion represents the greatest threat for migration into groundwater and entry into aquatic systems (Choudhary et al., 2024).

Phytoremediation, as an environmentally friendly, efficient, and cost-effective approach, is increasingly used for the remediation of soils and sediments contaminated with heavy metals (Akpor et al., 2014; Babu et al., 2021). This method utilizes the ability of certain plant species to absorb, translocate, and transform pollutants from the environment. Particularly important is phytoextraction, which enables the selective uptake of metals through plant roots and their translocation to the aboveground parts of the plant (Zeremski et al., 2021; Yan et al., 2020).

In this study, two sites containing dredged sediment were analyzed, where the total content and bioavailability of heavy metals were monitored over several consecutive years. At the same time, a phytoremediation process was implemented with the aim of reducing metal concentrations and limiting their mobility. Multi-year monitoring enabled the assessment of changes in metal concentrations and their fractional distribution, which is crucial for understanding their behavior in sediment and evaluating the risk of migration toward groundwater. The particular significance of this approach lies in the fact that the bioavailable fraction of metals represents the greatest threat for leaching and transport through the soil profile. The obtained results provide a comprehensive assessment of the potential risk to groundwater and form the basis for future decision-making related to the management of contaminated sites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

The research was conducted at a pilot site in Serbia, located along the Begej Canal near the Serbian–Romanian border. The site was divided into two enclosed sections, named Landfill 1 and Landfill 2, each covering an area of approximately 1200 m². These sections were established for the disposal of dredged sediment from the Begej Canal, for which sediment quality data collected during the period 2003–2015 (Dalmacija et al., 2006; Dubovina et al., 2018) consistently indicated contamination with heavy metals and specific organic pollutants. Landfill 1 contains sediment dredged in 2017, while Landfill 2 was covered with freshly deposited sediment at the end of 2021. This setup provided suitable conditions for conducting a multi-year experiment aimed at monitoring the behavior and mobility of heavy metals in sediment during the phytoremediation process.

2.1 Priprema zemljišta i fitoremedijacioni tretman

Na pripremljenom zemljištu, nakon osnovne obrade (oranje i tanjiranje) i predsetvene prihrane azotnim đubrivom, proces fitoremedijacije sproveden je u tri uzastopne vegetacione sezone (2021–2024) s ciljem procjene promjena u sadržaju, mobilnosti i biodostupnosti teških metala u sedimentu.

- Prva vegetaciona sezona (2021–2022): Tretman je sproveden isključivo na Deponiji 1 upotrebom uljane repice (*Brassica napus*).
- Druga vegetaciona sezona (2022–2023): Uljana repica (*Brassica napus*) zasijana je i na Deponiji 1 i na Deponiji 2.
- Treća vegetaciona sezona (2024): Na obje deponije zasijan je sirak (*Sorghum bicolor*) kao prolječna kultura, uz dvije kosidbe tokom vegetacije.

2.2 Uzorkovanje i priprema uzoraka sedimenta

Radi karakterizacije i praćenja promjena u sadržaju teških metala, uzorkovanje sedimenta sprovedeno je prije sjetve i nakon završetka svake vegetacione sezone. Deponija 1 je podijeljena na 10 eksperimentalnih (1–10) i 2 kontrolne sekcije (11 i 12), dok je Deponija 2 podijeljena na 10 eksperimentalnih sekcija (slika 1). Uzorci su prikupljeni sa površinskog sloja sedimenta, dubine 0–20 cm. Za svaku sekciju pripremljeni su kompozitni uzorci kombinovanjem tri pojedinačna uzorka.

2.1 Soil preparation and phytoremediation treatment

On the prepared soil, after basic tillage (plowing and disking) and pre-sowing fertilization with nitrogen fertilizer, the phytoremediation process was carried out over three consecutive growing seasons (2021–2024) to assess changes in the content, mobility, and bioavailability of heavy metals in the sediment.

- First growing season (2021–2022): The treatment was conducted exclusively on Landfill 1 using oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*).
- Second growing season (2022–2023): Oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*) was sown on both Landfill 1 and Landfill 2.
- Third growing season (2024): Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) was sown as a spring crop on both landfills, with two harvests during the vegetation period.

2.2 Sampling and preparation of sediment samples

For the characterization and monitoring of changes in heavy metal content, sediment sampling was conducted before sowing and after each vegetation season. Landfill 1 was divided into 10 experimental sections (1–10) and 2 control sections (11 and 12), while Landfill 2 was divided into 10 experimental sections (Figure 1). Samples were collected from the surface sediment layer at a depth of 0–20 cm. For each section, composite samples were prepared by combining three individual subsamples.

Slika 1. Deponija 1 (lijevo) podijeljena na 10 eksperimentalnih i 2 kontrolne sekcije i Deponija 2 (desno) podijeljena na 10 eksperimentalnih sekcija
Figure 1. Landfill 1 (left) divided into 10 experimental and 2 control sections, and Landfill 2 (right) divided into 10 experimental sections

2.3 Analiza prikupljenih uzoraka

Ukupan sadržaj teških metala u uzorcima sedimenta određen je nakon pripreme uzoraka postupkom mikrotalasne digestije (Milestone, Start E/0610030141) prema Metodi EPA 3051A. Za digestiju je masa od 1 g sedimenta odmjerena u teflonske kivete, nakon čega je dodat rastvor koncentrovanih kiselina u zapreminskom odnosu $\text{HNO}_3:\text{HCl}=3:1$ (9 mL koncentrovane azotne kiseline i 3 mL koncentrovane hlorovodonične kiseline). Uzorci su digestirani na temperaturi od 170 °C, a nakon hlađenja filtrirani su i dopunjeni dejonizovanom vodom u odmjerne sudove od 50 mL.

Biodostupni sadržaj teških metala u uzorcima sedimenta određen je primjenom BCR sekvencijalne ekstrakcije prema postupku opisanom u literaturi (Arain i sar., 2008). Ova metoda omogućava diferencijaciju metala po frakcijama (izmjenjiva, reducibilna, oksidabilna i rezidualna), čime se procjenjuje njihova potencijalna mobilnost i rizik od migracije u podzemne vode.

Ukupan sadržaj teških metala u sedimentu, kao i sadržaj teških metala u četiri frakcije po BCR sekvencijalnoj analizi, određen je na ICP–MS (Agilent Technologies 7700) prema Metodi EPA 6020B.

3. REZULTATI I DISKUSIJA

3.1 Analiza ukupnog sadržaja metala

Na slici 2 prikazane su prosječne vrijednosti ukupnog sadržaja hroma (Cr) i kadmijuma (Cd) u sedimentima na kontrolnoj lokaciji i na dvije eksperimentalne deponije (Deponija 1 i Deponija 2) tokom perioda 2021–2024. godine. Analize su sprovedene na dubini od 0–20 cm a prikazane vrijednosti predstavljaju srednje koncentracije za svaku godinu praćenja. Deponija 1 sadrži sediment izmuljen 2017. godine i predstavlja primjer dugoročnog „starog“ zagađenja, dok Deponija 2 sadrži svježe deponovan sediment iz 2021. godine. Iako je analiziran širi spektar teških metala, u radu su detaljno predstavljeni rezultati za Cr i Cd jer su upravo ovi metali identifikovani kao ključni pokazatelji rizika na ispitivanoj lokaciji. Kadmijum je pokazao veći udio mobilnih frakcija i izraženiju varijabilnost tokom monitoringa, dok je hrom dominantno prisutan u stabilnijim oblicima. Ovakav izbor omogućava poređenje metala različite mobilnosti i pruža reprezentativan model za procjenu ponašanja metala u svježe deponovanom i stabilizovanom sedimentu.

2.3 Analysis of collected samples

The total content of heavy metals in the sediment samples was determined after sample preparation using the microwave digestion method (Milestone, Start E/0610030141) in accordance with EPA Method 3051A. For digestion, 1 g of sediment was weighed into Teflon vessels, followed by the addition of a concentrated acid mixture in a volumetric ratio of $\text{HNO}_3:\text{HCl} = 3:1$ (9 mL of concentrated nitric acid and 3 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid). The samples were digested at 170 °C, then cooled, filtered, and diluted with deionized water to a final volume of 50 mL in volumetric flasks.

The bioavailable content of heavy metals in the sediment samples was determined using the BCR sequential extraction procedure as described in the literature (Arain et al., 2008). This method allows differentiation of metals into four fractions (exchangeable, reducible, oxidizable, and residual), enabling the assessment of their potential mobility and the risk of migration into groundwater.

The total content of heavy metals in the sediment, as well as the content of metals in the four fractions obtained by BCR sequential extraction, was determined using ICP–MS (Agilent Technologies 7700) in accordance with EPA Method 6020B.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis of total metal content

Figure 2 shows the average total concentrations of chromium (Cr) and cadmium (Cd) in sediments from the control site and the two experimental landfills (Landfill 1 and Landfill 2) during the 2021–2024 period. The analyses were performed at a depth of 0–20 cm, and the presented values represent mean concentrations for each monitoring year. Landfill 1 contains sediment dredged in 2017 and represents an example of long-term “aged” contamination, while Landfill 2 contains freshly deposited sediment from 2021. Although a broader range of heavy metals was analyzed, the results for Cr and Cd are presented in detail in this study because these metals were identified as key indicators of risk at the investigated site. Cadmium exhibited a higher proportion of mobile fractions and greater variability during the monitoring period, whereas chromium was predominantly present in more stable forms. This selection allows a comparison of metals with different mobility and provides a representative model for assessing metal behavior in freshly deposited and stabilized sediments.

Slika 2. Ukupni sadržaj teških metala u sedimentu tokom perioda 2021-2024.

Figure 2. Total heavy metal content in sediment during the period 2021–2024.

Rezultati pokazuju da su koncentracije oba analizirana metala bile značajno više na Deponiji 1 i Deponiji 2 u poređenju s kontrolnom lokacijom. Na kontrolnoj lokaciji koncentracije su tokom svih godina bile ispod granica koje se u literaturi navode kao granične vrijednosti za zagađene sedimente (Zeb i sar., 2024; Dorleon i sar., 2025).

Na Deponiji 1, koja sadrži sediment izmuljen 2017. godine, uočene su relativno više početne koncentracije metala koje tokom narednih godina pokazuju blage oscilacije. Ovakav trend u površinskim slojevima ukazuje na efikasnost fitoremedijacije i minimalan rizik od ispiranja metala u dublje slojeve. Slična zapažanja su istaknuta i u drugim istraživanjima, gdje je dokazano da su promjene u ukupnim koncentracijama metala u starijim, već deponovanim sedimentima, prilično spore i minimalne, jer zavise od kompleksnih geohemijskih uslova (Kafle i sar., 2022). Oscilacije u koncentracijama metala često se javljaju kao posljedica sezonskih promjena vlažnosti i ograničene pokretljivosti metala. Na Deponiji 2, koja sadrži svježe deponovan sediment, uočava se blagi porast koncentracija analiziranih metala od 2022. do 2024. godine. Takav trend ukazuje na procese unutrašnje redistribucije metala unutar profila sedimenta nakon deponovanja, što je posljedica promjene redoks uslova, oksidacije i povećane difuzije rastvorenih jona metala. Kod novodeponovanih, svježih sedimenata, povećanje ukupnog sadržaja metala u ranim fazama stabilizacije često je rezultat ovih dinamičnih geohemijskih procesa (Bucşe i sar., 2024; Chen i sar., 2025). Dodatno, tokom posljednje vegetacione sezone, mogući uzrok povećanih koncentracija metala u površinskim slojevima može biti hidraulička redistribucija iz dubljih

The results indicate that the concentrations of both analyzed metals were significantly higher at Landfill 1 and Landfill 2 compared to the control site. At the control site, concentrations remained below the threshold values for contaminated sediments reported in the literature throughout the study period (Zeb et al., 2024; Dorleon et al., 2025).

At Landfill 1, which contains sediment dredged in 2017, relatively higher initial metal concentrations were observed, showing slight oscillations over subsequent years. This trend in the surface layers indicates the effectiveness of phytoremediation and a minimal risk of metal leaching into deeper layers. Similar observations were reported by other studies, showing that changes in total metal concentrations in older, already stabilized sediments are typically slow and limited, as they depend on complex geochemical conditions (Kafle et al., 2022). Oscillations in metal concentrations often occur because of seasonal fluctuations in moisture and the limited mobility of metals. At Landfill 2, which contains freshly deposited sediment, a slight increase in the concentrations of analyzed metals was observed between 2022 and 2024. This trend indicates internal redistribution processes of metals within the sediment profile after deposition, resulting from changes in redox conditions, oxidation, and enhanced diffusion of dissolved metal ions. In newly deposited, fresh sediments, the increase in total metal content during the early stabilization phase is often a result of these dynamic geochemical processes (Bucşe et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2025). Additionally, during the last growing season, increased surface concentrations may have resulted from hydraulic redistribution from deeper horizons, particularly pronounced in deep-rooted

horizonata, što je naročito izraženo kod kultura sa dubokim korjenovim sistemom, poput sirka. Tokom perioda intenzivnih suša i povišenih temperatura (koje su se javile tokom ljeta 2024. godine) voda koja se transportuje iz dubljih slojeva putem korijena može sadržati rastvorene jone metala, koji se naknadno akumuliraju u zoni rizosfere i adsorbuju na čestice sedimenta u površinskom sloju.

Kadmijum pokazuje veću varijabilnost od hroma. Na obje deponije uočene su oscilacije u koncentracijama između godina, što je u skladu s njegovom visokom pokretljivošću i osjetljivošću na promjene fizičko-hemijskih uslova sredine (Coakley i sar., 2019). Suprotno kadmijumu, hrom pokazuje znatno stabilnije vrijednosti, sa manjim razlikama između godina i lokacija, što je u skladu sa njegovom niskom mobilnošću (Ahemad, 2015).

Uopšteno posmatrano, rezultati pokazuju da je ukupni sadržaj teških metala viši u svježem sedimentu (Deponija 2) nego u starijem (Deponija 1), što ukazuje na značajne razlike između novog i dugoročnog zagađenja. Ova razlika može biti posljedica vremena izlaganja, uslova sredine i hemijske stabilnosti samog sedimenta. Dobijeni rezultati odgovaraju tumačenjima drugih istraživanja u kojima je pokazano da svježije deponovani sedimenti obično sadrže veće koncentracije ukupnih metala, dok kod starijih sedimenata dolazi do njihovog postepenog smanjenja usljed prirodnih procesa i uticaja vegetacije (Zeb i sar., 2024; Dorleon i sar., 2025).

3.2 Analiza biodostupnosti metala

Pored ukupnog sadržaja metala, za procjenu njihovog toksičnog potencijala od izuzetnog je značaja poznavanje hemijskog oblika u kom se metali nalaze. Naime, raspodjela metala po frakcijama često ima jednaku važnost kao i njihov ukupni sadržaj, jer različiti oblici metala pokazuju različitu toksičnost, mobilnost i sposobnost migracije u životnoj sredini. Evropska zajednica za standardizaciju (European Community Bureau of Reference – BCR) razvila je standardizovani postupak sekvencijalne ekstrakcije koji omogućava razdvajanje metala na četiri frakcije: izmjenjivu, reducibilnu, oksidabilnu i rezidualnu. Prve dvije frakcije obuhvataju mobilnije oblike metala, koji se mogu osloboditi već pri manjoj promjeni pH vrijednosti ili jonske jačine rastvora, te predstavljaju potencijalno biodostupne oblike. Ovakav pristup omogućava pouzdaniju procjenu rizika, jer pruža uvid u dio ukupnog sadržaja metala koji može biti dostupan biljkama ili mobilisan u životnu sredinu (Li i sar., 2022).

crops such as sorghum. During periods of intense drought and elevated temperatures (recorded in the summer of 2024), water transported upward through roots from deeper layers may have carried dissolved metal ions, which subsequently accumulated in the rhizosphere and adsorbed onto sediment particles in the surface layer.

Cadmium exhibited greater variability than chromium. On both landfills, fluctuations in concentrations were observed between years, consistent with its high mobility and sensitivity to changes in the physicochemical conditions of the environment (Coakley et al., 2019). In contrast to cadmium, chromium showed much more stable values, with smaller differences between years and locations, which aligns with its low mobility (Ahemad, 2015).

Overall, the results indicate that the total content of heavy metals was higher in the freshly deposited sediment (Landfill 2) than in the older one (Landfill 1), reflecting significant differences between recent and long-term contamination. This difference may be attributed to exposure time, environmental conditions, and the chemical stability of the sediment itself. The obtained results are consistent with previous studies showing that freshly deposited sediments generally contain higher total metal concentrations, while in older sediments, gradual reductions occur due to natural processes and the influence of vegetation (Zeb et al., 2024; Dorleon et al., 2025).

3.2 Analysis of heavy metal bioavailability

In addition to the total metal content, understanding the chemical form in which metals occur is of great importance for assessing their toxic potential. The distribution of metals among fractions is often as significant as their total concentration, since different forms exhibit varying levels of toxicity, mobility, and migration capacity in the environment. The European Community Bureau of Reference (BCR) developed a standardized sequential extraction procedure that allows metals to be divided into four fractions: exchangeable, reducible, oxidizable, and residual. The first two fractions include the more mobile forms of metals, which can be released even with slight changes in pH or ionic strength of the solution, and therefore represent potentially bioavailable forms. This approach enables a more reliable risk assessment by providing insight into the portion of the total metal content that can be available to plants or mobilized in the environment (Li et al., 2022).

Slika 3. Rezultati BCR sekvencijalne ekstrakcije u površinskom sloju sedimenta tokom perioda 2021–2024. godina (K-kontrola, D1-Deponija 1, D2-Deponija 2)

Na slici 3 prikazana je raspodjela Cr i Cd po frakcijama dobijenim primjenom BCR sekvencijalne ekstrakcije u površinskom sloju sedimenta (0–20 cm) na kontrolnoj lokaciji i na dvije eksperimentalne deponije (Deponija 1 i Deponija 2) tokom perioda 2021–2024. godine. Prikazane vrijednosti predstavljaju prosječne udjele metala u izmjenljivoj, reducirabilnoj, oksidabilnoj i rezidualnoj frakciji.

Raspodjela metala između frakcija jasno pokazuje razlike u mobilnosti i stepenu stabilizacije u zavisnosti od starosti sedimenta. Na kontrolnoj lokaciji dominira rezidualna frakcija, naročito kod hroma, što ukazuje na visok stepen stabilnosti i minimalan rizik od ispiranja u dublje slojeve. Kod kadmijuma je u kontrolnim uzorcima, pored stabilnih frakcija, zabilježen i uočljiv udio reducirabilne frakcije, što ukazuje na mogućnost njegove ograničene mobilnosti u promjenjivim redoks uslovima. Na Deponiji 1, koja sadrži stariji sediment, hrom se tokom svih godina nalazi gotovo isključivo u oksidabilnoj i rezidualnoj frakciji, uz mali udio reducirabilne komponente koji se blago smanjuje s vremenom. Takav trend ukazuje da je tokom višegodišnje stabilizacije i djelovanja vegetacije došlo do vezivanja hroma za organske i mineralne komponente, što značajno smanjuje njegovu biodostupnost i rizik od migracije u podzemne vode. Kadmijum na istoj lokaciji pokazuje veći udio reducirabilne frakcije u ranijem periodu (2021–2022), dok se u kasnijim godinama bilježi porast oksidabilne

Figure 3. Results of BCR sequential extraction in the surface sediment layer during the period 2021–2024 (C–Control, L1–Landfill 1, L2–Landfill 2)

Figure 3 shows the distribution of chromium and cadmium across fractions obtained using the BCR sequential extraction procedure in the surface sediment layer (0–20 cm) at the control site and two experimental landfills (Landfill 1 and Landfill 2) during the 2021–2024 period. The presented values represent the average proportion of metals in the exchangeable, reducible, oxidizable, and residual fractions.

The distribution of metals among fractions clearly demonstrates differences in mobility and stabilization depending on the sediment age. At the control site, the residual fraction dominates, particularly for chromium, indicating a high degree of stability and minimal risk of leaching into deeper layers. In the case of cadmium, besides the stable fractions, a noticeable share of the reducible fraction was observed, suggesting limited potential for migration under fluctuating redox conditions. At Landfill 1, which contains older sediment, chromium was found almost exclusively in the oxidizable and residual fractions throughout all years, with a small share of the reducible fraction that gradually decreased over time. This trend indicates that during long-term stabilization and vegetation activity, chromium became increasingly bound to organic and mineral components, significantly reducing its bioavailability and risk of migration to groundwater. Cadmium at the same site showed a higher share of the reducible fraction in the early period (2021–2022), followed by

i smanjenje izmjenjive frakcije, što ukazuje na njegovu djelimičnu imobilizaciju tokom procesa fitoremedijacije i prirodne stabilizacije sedimenta. Suprotno tome, na Deponiji 2, koja sadrži svježe deponovan sediment, uočava se veći udio izmjenjive i reducibilne frakcije kod oba metala, naročito kod kadmijuma, gdje mobilni oblici čine više od polovine ukupnog sadržaja. Takva raspodjela ukazuje na prisustvo metalnih oblika koji se lako oslobađaju pri manjim promjenama pH ili redoks potencijala, čime raste vjerovatnoća njihove mobilizacije i vertikalnog transporta ka podzemnim vodama. Kod hroma se u istom periodu primjećuje umjeren porast reducibilne i oksidabilne frakcije, što sugerise aktivne procese vezivanja na Fe/Mn okside i organske komplekse, ali uz još uvijek ograničenu stabilnost sistema (Liu i sar., 2024; Osae i sar., 2022).

Razlike između lokacija potvrđuju da procesi starenja i fitoremedijacije dovode do smanjenja udjela mobilnih frakcija i povećanja stabilnih oblika metala. Stariji sediment (Deponija 1) karakterise manja biodostupnost i niži rizik od kontaminacije podzemnih voda, dok svježi sediment (Deponija 2) i dalje sadrži visoko mobilne forme, naročito kadmijuma, koje predstavljaju potencijalni izvor zagađenja u slučaju promjene uslova u zoni zasićenja (Osae i sar., 2022; Matabane i sar., 2021; Coakley i sar., 2019; Ahemad, 2015).

4. ZAKLJUČAK

Rezultati višegodišnjeg monitoringa pokazali su da se sadržaj i raspodjela teških metala u sedimentima značajno razlikuju u zavisnosti od starosti i stepena stabilizacije deponovanog materijala. Ukupne koncentracije metala bile su više na eksperimentalnim deponijama u odnosu na kontrolnu lokaciju, što potvrđuje prisustvo zagađenja uslovljenog prethodnim taloženjem kontaminiranog sedimenta. Na starijem sedimentu (Deponija 1) uočene su stabilnije vrijednosti i manja varijabilnost, dok je na svježem (Deponija 2) zabilježen blagi porast koncentracija metala. Rezultati BCR sekvencijalne ekstrakcije potvrdili su da procesi starenja i stabilizacije sedimenta imaju ključnu ulogu u smanjenju biodostupnosti metala. Na starijem sedimentu dominiraju stabilne frakcije (oksidabilna i rezidualna), dok u svježem i dalje preovlađuju mobilniji oblici, naročito kadmijuma, što ukazuje na povećan rizik od migracije metala u podzemne vode. Višegodišnja fitoremedijacija doprinijela je daljoj stabilizaciji metala u površinskom sloju sedimenta, usljed procesa usvajanja od strane biljaka, zadržavanja u rizosferi i vezivanja za organske komponente.

an increase in the oxidizable and a decrease in the exchangeable fraction in later years, indicating its partial immobilization during the phytoremediation process and natural sediment stabilization. In contrast, Landfill 2, which contains freshly deposited sediment, shows a higher proportion of exchangeable and reducible fractions for both metals, particularly cadmium, where mobile forms account for more than half of the total content. Such distribution indicates the presence of metal species that can be easily released under minor changes in pH or redox potential, increasing the likelihood of their mobilization and vertical transport toward groundwater. For chromium, a moderate increase in the reducible and oxidizable fractions was observed during the same period, suggesting active binding to Fe/Mn oxides and organic complexes but still limited system stability (Liu et al., 2024; Osae et al., 2022).

Differences between the sites confirm that processes of aging and phytoremediation lead to a reduction in mobile fractions and an increase in stable metal forms. The older sediment (Landfill 1) is characterized by lower bioavailability and reduced groundwater contamination risk, while the fresh sediment (Landfill 2) still contains highly mobile forms, particularly cadmium, which represent a potential source of pollution in the event of changes in saturation zone conditions (Osae et al., 2022; Matabane et al., 2021; Coakley et al., 2019; Ahemad, 2015).

4. CONCLUSION

The results of long-term monitoring showed that the content and distribution of heavy metals in sediments vary significantly depending on the age and degree of stabilization of the deposited material. Total metal concentrations were higher at the experimental landfills compared to the control site, confirming the presence of contamination caused by the previous deposition of polluted sediment. In the older sediment (Landfill 1), more stable values and lower variability were observed, while in the fresh sediment (Landfill 2), a slight increase in metal concentrations was recorded. The results of the BCR sequential extraction confirmed that the processes of aging and sediment stabilization play a crucial role in reducing metal bioavailability. In the older sediment, stable fractions (oxidizable and residual) dominate, while in the fresh sediment, more mobile forms, particularly those of cadmium, are still prevalent, indicating a higher risk of metal migration into groundwater. Long-term phytoremediation contributed to further metal stabilization in the surface sediment layer through plant uptake, retention in the rhizosphere, and binding to organic components.

Rezultati ovog istraživanja potvrđuju da rizik od zagađenja podzemnih voda zavisi prvenstveno od hemijskog oblika i stepena stabilizacije metala, a ne samo od njihovog ukupnog sadržaja. Integrirani pristup koji obuhvata praćenje i ukupnih i biodostupnih frakcija metala predstavlja pouzdanu osnovu za procjenu ekološkog rizika i razvoj strategija održivog upravljanja kontaminiranim sedimentima. U praktičnom smislu, rezultati ukazuju da svježe deponovani sedimenti zahtijevaju poseban nadzor i kontinuirani monitoring biodostupnih frakcija metala prilikom planiranja njihovog daljeg upravljanja.

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The findings of this study confirm that the risk of groundwater contamination depends primarily on the chemical form and degree of metal stabilization rather than solely on their total content. An integrated approach that includes monitoring both total and bioavailable metal fractions provides a reliable basis for assessing ecological risk and developing sustainable management strategies for contaminated sediments. In practical terms, the results indicate that freshly deposited sediments require special attention and continuous monitoring of bioavailable metal fractions when planning their further management.

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